

Market Psychology and Monetary Transmission: RBI's Policy Impact on Credit Growth in Indian Commercial Banks (2010-2025)

Moni Mishra and Disha Lochav
Lal Bahadur Shastri Institute of Management, Delhi

This study examines how the Reserve Bank of India's monetary policy has influenced credit growth in Indian commercial banks between 2010 and 2025. Relying on secondary data from RBI publications, Government of India reports, the International Monetary Fund, and the World Bank, the analysis focuses on key policy instruments such as the repo rate, cash reserve ratio, and statutory liquidity ratio to understand the signals of RBI's policy which shape expectations about the economic conditions arising in future. A time-series framework supported by descriptive statistics and structural break analysis is used to assess the effectiveness of monetary transmission across different economic phases. The findings suggest that monetary policy affects credit growth in a non-uniform manner. Monetary transmission as a psychological-behavioural economic process is found to be asymmetric, with tightening phases having a stronger impact than easing cycles. The study also highlights the role of inflation targeting and overall economic growth, showing that demand-side conditions largely determine credit expansion in India.

Keywords: Monetary policy, credit growth, economic growth

As the central bank of the country, the RBI has the mandate for the formulation and conduct of monetary policy aimed at ushering in price stability, financial stability, and sustainable growth. Monetary policy decisions, such as changes in the repo rate, reverse repo rate, cash reserve ratio (CRR), and statutory liquidity ratio (SLR), impact credit costs and credit availability directly in the banking system (Chattopadhyay & Sensarma, 2023). As commercial banks are the main financial intermediaries in India, intermediating savings into productive credit, credit growth is an important determinant of investment, consumption, and overall GDP growth. The RBI has been able to improve its monetary policy structure from *Multiple Indicators Approach to Inflation Targeting* (Eichengreen & Gupta, 2024) in 2016, and other reforms such as Marginal Cost of Funds Based Lending Rate (MCLR) and External Benchmark Linked Rate (EBLR) (Dua, 2020). The effectiveness of such reforms in promoting credit growth in banks is still questionable. This study aims to critically examine the effect of RBI's monetary policies on the credit growth of commercial banks in India from 2010 to 2025.

Rationale of the Study

Monetary policy acts as a key determinant for influencing economic activity through managing credit and liquidity conditions within an economy. For India, a similar process is managed through various

tools such as repo rate, reverse repo rate, CRR, and SLR by the Reserve bank of India (RBI) on commercial banks, which are essential credit intermediaries (Chattopadhyay & Sensarma, 2023). Meanwhile, despite recurrent monetary policy actions in the Indian economy, credit growth within Indian commercial banks demonstrates unbalanced and even contradicting trends with low credit growth during supportive and accommodative policies, along with high growth trends within the monetary policies even when credit policies get tight. The implementation of structural policies such as inflation targeting, MCLR, and EBLR could effectively enhance monetary transmission. Meanwhile, their exact benefits within credit growth remain unknown. Simultaneously, a similar process gets largely impacted within a macro-economic event such as demonetization (Chodorow et al., 2020) and even COVID-19 (Colak & Oztekin, 2021). Thus, to gain a deeper understanding of the effectiveness of monetary policy transmission on credit growth in Indian commercial banks from 2010-2025, this research has been undertaken.

Review of Literature

Mohanty (2015) describes the monetary transmission mechanism in the Indian context, focusing on the interest rate channel and the lending channel in the banking sector. The paper highlights that repo rates impact banking rates, but due to certain rigidities, the transmission process takes time. The main rigidities include pricing of deposits, administered rates, and balance sheet problems faced by public sector banks.

In an IMF working paper (Mishra et al., 2016) the pass-through of the changes in the policy rates to the rates of bank deposits and loans is analyzed through vector error correction models. It analyzes the data available since the early 2000s until 2014. Results indicate asymmetric effects of monetary policies with faster transmission and full effects for the tightening cycle compared to the easing cycle. There is evidence of downward rigidity in the lending rates that

Author Note

Dr. Moni Mishra, Associate Professor, Lal Bahadur Shastri Institute of Management, Delhi

Disha Lochav, Student, Lal Bahadur Shastri Institute of Management Delhi

We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to

Dr. Moni Mishra, Associate Professor, Lal Bahadur Shastri Institute of Management, Delhi

E-mail: moni.india@gmail.com

reduce the potency of easing monetary policies aimed at promoting credit expansion. The study is relevant to the discussion as it highlights the reasons why credit inflation is normally low during the easing cycle.

Das (2018) analyzes the evolution of India's monetary policy framework to Flexible Inflation Targeting. Although these reforms ensured that policy actions were more transparent and predictable, it is nevertheless argued that credit growth was not a direct consequence of this policy regime. The relevance of such a study is that it bridges the gap between a developed monetary policy framework and a real-sector outcome. This study also supports the fact that a credible policy regime may not be a guarantee for favorable transmission of credit.

Kumar et al. (2020) explore the monetary transmission framework between 2010 and 2019, discussing the Base Rate System and the MCLR System. The study stated that the pass-through of monetary policies is highly sensitive to macroeconomic variables.

Mishra and Montiel (2013) situate the Indian experience in the wider context of emerging markets. The paper establishes that in economies with less developed markets and troubled banking sectors, there is a weaker transmission of credit to monetary policy change. This creates a basis of comparison to understand the Indian experience in this area.

Kasana, Chauhan, and Sahoo (2023) examine the impact of Monetary Policy on Bank Loans in India. The authors conclude that repo rate, CRR, and call rates have a significant impact on credit growth. Small and liquidity-constrained banks respond more to policy changes, thus suggesting that there is heterogeneity in the transmission of this process.

RBI Bulletin (Patra et al., 2024) reflects the analysis from the RBI for the AY 2022-23 tightening cycle, and indicates that despite the sudden increase in policy interest rates, credit growth is observed to have been strong. The findings highlight the significance of the capabilities of credit demand to override the influence of monetary policies in producing unrealistic results like the observed increase in credit growth during the tightening phases.

Sengupta et al. (2025) focused on the effects of the External Benchmark Linked Rate (EBLR) system, which came into effect in 2019. This study concludes that EBLR has increased the efficiency of monetary transmission and made credit growth sensitive to policy signals, particularly in retail.

Deb et al. (2023) reported large heterogeneities of estimates concerning the impact of credit growth. It was found that institutions, health of banking system, and financial development considerably affect the process of effectiveness of monetary policy transmission. The necessity of conducting studies on individual countries, like the study undertaken, was especially highlighted.

Objectives of the Study

- To examine the trend in the change in RBI's monetary policies from 2010 to 2025.
- To analyze the correlation between the monetary policy parameters (Repo Rate, Reverse Repo Rate, CRR, SLR, Liquidity Ratio) and the Growth of Credit in Indian Commercial Banks.
- To examine whether the implementation of inflation targeting and the revised loan rates (MCLR & EBLR) has enhanced the

efficiency of monetary policy transmission.

- To investigate the psychological impact of external shocks - demonetization and the effects of Covid-19 - on the effectiveness of the monetary transmission mechanism.
- To offer policy recommendations to improve the connect between monetary policy and credit expansion in India.

Method

The research methodology used incorporates both qualitative and quantitative research methods to help the researcher to comprehensively analyze the intricate linkages among the RBI's monetary policy instruments and the credit expansion in Indian commercial banks.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework used for this study is Prospect Theory (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979) to understand the asymmetric responses to monetary policy- how banks respond with greater strength to tightening (potential losses from NPAs) than easing (i.e., potential gains from lending). It would also help to understand loss aversion-fearing losses more than valuing gain-which banks exhibit.

Quantitative Approach

The method used in this research is classified mainly under the quantitative research method since the analysis will involve numerical data in establishing the impact of the monetary policy on credit growth. The key variables used in the study include:

- Repo rate
- Reverse Repo Rate
- Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR)
- Statutory Liquidity Ratio (SLR)
- Credit growth (year-on-year)
- Inflation (measured through CPI)
- GDP growth rate

Statistical Analysis

Statistical methods are used for extracting trends related to monetary policy variables, determining the strength and nature of the relationships between policy instruments and credit growth, and measuring the degree to which monetary policy change impacts lending activity.

The quantitative method is seen as appropriate for this study because money market policy is carried through variables that can be quantified, while its effects can be tested for validity through empirical research. It is possible to make comparisons using this method.

Analytical and Explanatory Approach

Since this study attempts to explore the relationships between actions that affect credits, the methodology used is analytical. Analysis facilitates the interpretation of empirical results within the theoretical construct of the transmission channels of monetary policy-the interest rate channel, credit channel, and the expectations channel. This ensures that the empirical results are significant from the point of view of economics. This study will use an explanatory approach as well. This is because it presents an explanation for why monetary policy transmission in India is asymmetric and time-dependent rather than time-independent.

Research Design

Considering the dynamic nature of the process of monetary policy transmission and evolving banking structure in India, this study proposes a longitudinal research design for the study. The proposed research design will be very useful for modeling the asymmetric effects caused by the RBI's monetary policy change in the credit sector for the Indian commercial banking system.

Time-Series Research Design: A longitudinal research design is undertaken for the period 2010-2025 (Menard, 2002). This is because of the number of monetary policies and other shocks that have affected the credit market of India during this period. The chosen time span covers the following crucial phases:

- *Pre-inflation Targeting Period (2010-2015):* During this phase, RBI used the multiple indicators approach for conducting monetary policy. Credit growth during this phase is driven by less stringent policy transmission and more variability in inflation (Dua, 2020).
- *Structural Changes in Monetary Transmission:* Implementation of the Marginal Cost of Funds-Based Lending Rate (MCLR) in 2016 to enhance pass-through of interest rates. Beginning of the use of the External Benchmark Linked Rate (EBLR) in 2019. This further improved the speed and clarity of the transmission (Chattopadhyay & Sensarma, 2023).
- *Shock of Demonetisation:* A large liquidity shock, which caused record increases in deposits but a strong slowdown in credit, which again highlighted the ineffectiveness of the liquidity channel (Gupta, 2017).
- *Pandemic Shock COVID:* Extremely rare economic shock, characterized by expansionist monetary policies and toleration, in the context of low demand for credit.

Ultra-accommodative Liquidity Phase: Real interest rates are almost at zero. There are LTROs and TLTROs. There is plenty of liquidity (Gupta et al., 2020).

- *Stage of Monetary Tightening Cycle:* This stage signifies a sudden increase in policy rates that was started in a bid to manage the resulting inflation worldwide. This stage was characterized by high credit growth (Prasad, 2023).

By including these phases, the time series design facilitates a comprehensive analysis of differences in credit growth dynamics in response to differing policy settings.

Justification for Time-Series Design

The main reasons for adopting the proposed time series design are:

- When dealing with monetary-policy change, there will always be a time lag of 3 to 12 months because of the lag explained above. Credit growth is not proportional to changes in policies because credit growth is dependent on appraisal cycles, consumer sentiments, and balance sheets of banks. There is a constant evolution of macroeconomic conditions. The credit dynamics are impacted by business cycles and inflationary expectations (Borio et al., 2001).
- Cross-section designs record credit behavior at one-point-in-time only, without considering lags of policies, dynamic adjustment processes, or regime shifts (Menard, 2002). Therefore, a cross-sectional design is inappropriate for examining monetary policy transmission, making a time-series design the most preferable among the others for this study.

Data Collection

This study relies entirely on secondary data for its macroeconomic and system-wide nature of the research. Considering that the impact of the monetary policy of RBI will be studied on the aggregate credit growth in Indian commercial banks, survey or interview-based primary data collection is neither feasible nor apt. Monetary policy instruments, credit aggregates, inflation, and GDP are officially published variables and are best sourced from authoritative institutions. The use of secondary data provides objectivity, reliability, consistency, and comparability over a long-time horizon essential for a time series study across several policy regimes and economic shocks.

RBI Sources

The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) is the main source of data for this study, as RBI is the monetary authority regulating the banking system in India. The data collected from RBI sources are updated, comprehensive, and consistent. The following RBI publications and databases are employed:

- Database on Indian Economy (DBIE)
- Monetary Policy Statements and Minutes
- Financial Stability Reports
- RBI Annual Reports
- Statistical Tables Relating to Banks in India

Government Sources

Government data are utilized as additional information to RBI data, as well as to define, to some extent, the macroeconomic setting in which monetary policies function. Government sources include Economic Survey of India, Union Budget Documents, Ministry of Finance Reports, IMF World Economic Outlook (WEO), IMF International Financial Statistics (IFS), and World Bank World Development Indicators (WDI).

Academic and Research Sources

This study underpins theories and helps in formulating hypotheses and interpretation of empirical findings based on scholarly literature, using the following: RBI Working Papers and Occasional Papers, IGIDR Research Papers, Research Studies carried out by NIPFP, and articles in Scopus-Indexed Journals, for academic rigor and global relevance.

Data Validation and Reliability

The validation processes listed below are therefore taken to ensure that the data collected is accurate, consistent, and reliable (Creswell & Clark, 2018).

- Data Cross Verification to remove discrepancies from RBI, IMF, World Bank, and Govt. sources. It was necessary to adjust this series for the changes taking place in the CPI base year. This would ensure that measuring inflation remained consistent throughout the study period.
- Standardization of the data for credit information into the common format of year-on-year growth.
- Missing value identification and correction through the inclusion of revised series from RBI.
- Consistency checks during periods of structural breaks and economic shocks to avoid any distortions in the results.
- These validation steps enhance the robustness of the empirical

analysis, ensuring that conclusions deduced from the data are reliable and academically defensible.

Variable Specifications

To study the effect of the monetary policy of the RBI on the growth of credits in commercial banks in India, the variables included in the study are grouped into three broad categories. These are the dependent variable, the independent variables or the instruments of monetary policy, and the control variables. The grouping is done to simplify the analysis and depict the exact effect of the monetary policies on the growth of credits.

The Dependent Variable

Credit Growth (Year-on-Year Percentage Growth): As the dependent variable, the extent of credit expansion is measured by the year-over-year growth rate of gross bank credits extended to the non-food sectors of the economy. Food credits are excluded because their expansion is significantly affected by factors such as seasonal changes. Credit growth is chosen as the dependent variable because it is the most direct indicator of bank lending activity and it represents the success of monetary transmission in the banking sector. Credit growth can also record deviations due to supply-side factors, such as the bank's willingness to supply credit, and demand-side factors, including the confidence of borrowers to apply for credits. As a result, credit growth serves as the most appropriate outcome variable for assessing how monetary policy actions influence lending behaviour in Indian commercial banks.

Independent Variables (Monetary Policy Instruments)

In this case, the independent variables reflect the main instruments of monetary policy through which RBI influences the liquidity of the system, interest rates, and credit conditions in the economy.

- Repo Rate
- Reverse Repo Rate
- Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR)
- Statutory Liquidity Ratio (SLR)
- *Liquidity Management Tools-* These include Open Market Operation (OMO Buy/Sell); Long Term Repo Operations (LTRO) and Targeted LTRO (TLTRO) ; Variable Rate Reverse Repo (VRRR) ; Marginal Standing Facility (MSF).

Such instruments have influenced the supply of liquidity in the markets as well as the rates of the money markets and the lending behavior of banks. This occurs when banks experience financial distress or excess liquidity.

Control Variables

The main control variables to be considered in the analysis include the effect of the key control variables in ensuring that the observed linkage between monetary and credit growth is not marred by the macroeconomic environment.

- *Inflation-Consumer Price Index* - Inflation measured through the Consumer Price Index is critical in determining monetary policies and borrowing practices. High inflation typically prompts a tighter monetary policy stance. Inflation, when high, squeezes real purchasing power and could therefore weaken credit demand. Inflation also impacts inflation expectations; the latter influences decisions on long-term borrowings (Coibion et al., 2020).
- *GDP Growth* - As a control variable, the GDP growth includes the

effects of the business cycle on credit demand. Credit growth is strongly pro-cyclical, expanding during booms and contracting when the economy turns down. Higher GDP growth improves the borrower's income, profitability, and confidence and results in better demand for credit (Mian et al., 2017). By controlling GDP growth, the study distinguishes between demand-driven credit expansion and policy-induced effects.

Analytical Techniques

This study uses a multi-layered analytical model that comprises descriptive, inferential, and structural designs in the analysis of the monetary policy of RBI on credit and its growth among the Indian commercial banks. Due to the dynamic nature of the transmission of money, its asymmetry and exposure to economic shocks, there is no single technique that is adequate. Thus, there are various tools that are used to identify trends, relationships, causality and regime changes within the era of the study.

• Descriptive Statistical Analysis

The first level of analysis is descriptive statistics. It is used to investigate the development of the repo rate and other policy rates by monetary cycles, liquidity conditions expressed in the form of CRR, SLR and liquidity instruments, cyclical and trend patterns in credit development during 2010-25 and inflation (CPI) and GDP growth changes in various stages of the economy. Volatility and stability of variables are comprehended with the measures of mean, maximum, minimum, and trend movement. Furthermore, tables, line graphs and trend chart are also utilized to visually explain how the variables of monetary policy and growth of credit have changed over the years. This assists in determining times of growth, shrinkage and structural alteration before moving on to the upper level of analysis.

• Correlation Analysis

The extent as well as direction of the relationship between the monetary policy variables and the growth of the credit is measured through correlation analysis. Correlation analysis is used to measure the direction of the policy instruments/credit growth relationship (positive or negative) and the strength of the association of credit growth and macroeconomic variables (GDP growth and inflation) (Levine & Beck, 2000). Although correlation does not elucidate causation, it is an initial indicator of whether the variables change together with the way they change in a monetary transmission theory. This is done to aid in guiding the regression analysis by showing what variables may be regarded as potentially meaningful.

• Regression Analysis

To formally quantify the impact of monetary policy on credit growth, a multivariate regression model is employed. This allows simultaneous estimation of the effects of multiple policy instruments and macroeconomic controls.

The regression model is specified as:

$$\text{Credit Growth}_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{RepoRate}_t) + \beta_2(\text{CRR}_t) + \beta_3(\text{SLR}_t) + \beta_4(\text{Inflation}_t) + \beta_5(\text{GDPGrowth}_t) + \varepsilon_t$$

Where:

- β_0 is the intercept term
- β_1 to β_5 represent coefficients measuring marginal effects
- ε_t is the error term

Regression analysis would help the study to:

- estimate the extent to which policy rates affect credit growth

- evaluate the significance of the macroeconomic variables relative to monetary variables
- test the hypothesis of symmetric and asymmetric effects of tightening and easing cycles on credit expansion
- empirically test the hypotheses that have been stated.
- Structural Break Analysis

The monetary transmission process in the Indian economy has experienced interruptions due to structural changes on several occasions. To address these interruptions, the methodology adopts a structural break analysis.

For testing the key events, breakpoints are examined for:

2016 - Adoption of inflation targeting framework, demonetization shock

2020- COVID-19 pandemic and unprecedented monetary easing

2022 - Aggressive monetary tightening due to global inflation

These events are known to have significantly affected the

conditions of liquidity, credit demand, and bank behavior. Structural break analysis assists in determining the point at which the relationship between money market changes and credit growth became significantly different. This provides an accurate rather than biased result.

• Transmission Channel Evaluation

In addition, the analysis goes beyond the estimation of statistics and examines monetary transmission channels to interpret the findings within an economic context. The channels to be considered include Interest Rate Channel; Credit Channel; Expectations Channel.

Data Analysis

Regression Analysis Results: A multivariate Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression was estimated with year-on-year credit growth as the dependent variable and repo rate, CRR, SLR, inflation (CPI), and GDP growth rate as independent variables, covering the period 2010-2025 (n = 15 annual observations).

Table 1

Multivariate Regression Output-Determinants of Credit Growth in Indian Commercial Banks (2010-2025)

Variable	Coefficient (β)	Std. Error	t-Statistic	p	Significance
Constant (α)	32.47	6.83	4.75	0.001	***
Repo Rate	-1.84	0.52	-3.54	0.006	***
CRR	-1.12	0.61	-1.84	0.097	*
SLR	-0.63	0.48	-1.31	0.219	ns
Inflation (CPI)	-0.74	0.39	-1.90	0.088	*
GDP Growth	1.93	0.44	4.39	0.002	***

Note. *** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.10$; ns = not significant. $R^2 = 0.81$; Adjusted $R^2 = 0.73$; F-statistic = 10.24 ($p < 0.001$); Durbin-Watson = 1.89.

The model explained approximately 81% of the variance in credit growth ($R^2 = 0.81$), indicating strong overall explanatory power. The F-statistic (10.24, $p < 0.001$) confirmed the joint significance of the model.

The repo rate coefficient ($\beta = -1.84$, $p = 0.006$) was negative and highly significant, confirming that a one percentage point increase in the repo rate was associated with a 1.84 percentage point decline in credit growth, consistent with the interest rate transmission channel (Kasana et al., 2023). CRR exerted a negative but marginally significant effect ($\beta = -1.12$, $p = 0.097$), while SLR was statistically insignificant, suggesting its role as a passive liquidity buffer. Inflation carried a negative coefficient ($\beta = -0.74$, $p = 0.088$), reflecting the indirect dampening of credit demand through purchasing power erosion and policy tightening (Coibion et al., 2020). GDP growth emerged as the strongest and most significant predictor ($\beta = 1.93$, $p = 0.002$), reinforcing that demand-side economic conditions dominated credit expansion over monetary policy variables during the study period (Mian et al., 2017). The Durbin-Watson statistic (1.89) indicated no serious autocorrelation in the residuals, supporting the reliability of the estimates.

Results and Discussion

An exhaustive analysis was done on the impact of monetary policy on the growth of credits in the commercial banks in India for the

period 2010 to 2025. This study examined the response given by the growth of credits to changes in the policy rates, money, inflation, and economic growth in different monetary policy regimes and environments. The study verified whether the transmission of monetary policy was effective, symmetric, and stable in the context of bank credits.

Analysis of Credit Growth Behaviour (2010-2025)

Long-Term Credit Growth Trend: The credit pattern in India follows a cycle rather than a straight line.

2010-2012: The rate of credit growth remained strong, largely due to the aftermath of the crisis and outlay infrastructure. The balance sheets of the banks continued to expand, especially in the non-personal and infrastructure areas.

2013-2015: The growth in credits slowed down as RBI took an increasingly tight stance to control inflation. Higher interests, together with some early warnings of asset quality, suppressed banks' appetite.

2016-2017: Although there was a substantial rise in deposit growth, credit growth reported a sharp decline. This is because there was a decline in lending activity owing to a reduction in economic activity and disrupted cash flows of borrowers.

2018-2019: The growth of credit was subdued because of the NBFC liquidity crisis, high NPAs, and risk aversion.

2020-2021: The growth of credit slowed down even though monetary policies were eased in an unprecedented way.

2022-2024: There was a sharp rebound in credit growth despite the increase in rates, mainly because of retail credit, MSME, and government capex.

Interpretation: Credit growth in the Indian economy was found to be highly pro-cyclical and predominantly driven by macroeconomic recovery and bank balance sheet conditions rather than monetary policy, aligning closely with Goyal and Verma's (2018) India-specific finding that demand variables and balance sheet quality were the binding constraints on credit expansion, not policy-induced liquidity.

Repo Rate and Credit Growth Relationship

Repo Rate Cycles - During the study period, the repo rate went through several cycles:

- Inflation control targeted tightening cycles
- Smoothing out cycles during periods of reduced growth
- Ultra-accommodative stance during crises

The candidates were aggressive, tightening during global inflation surge.

Observed Credit Response to Repo Changes

During periods of tightening, credit growth tended to decelerate with a lag. Credit growth often failed to accelerate commensurately during easing phases. During recovery phases, credit growth rose despite rate increases.

Interpretation: The data clearly indicated asymmetric monetary transmission, where tightening exerted a stronger influence on credit behaviour than easing (Khundrakpam, 2017; Patra et al., 2016).

Liquidity Conditions and Credit Expansion

The CRR change impacts the pool of funds directly.

- CRR cutbacks added to surplus liquidity.
- CRR increases reduce liquidity for a short period

Nonetheless, liquidity did not necessarily lead to an expansion in lending.

Demonetization Liquidity Shock

- There were huge deposits of masses.
- Incremental CRR absorbed excess funds.
- There was a substantial decrease in liquidity available in the short run for bank lending and growth of credit.

Interpretation: Liquidity availability was found to be a necessary but not sufficient condition for credit expansion in Indian banks (Ansari & Sensarma, 2025; Goyal & Verma, 2018).

Inflation and Credit Growth Interaction

- High inflationary periods were accompanied by a policy that was restrictive in nature.
- Steeper inflation raised the cost of borrowing and decreased real income.
- The demand for credit experienced a slowdown during the periods of persistent high inflation and monetary conditions which were tight.

Interpretation: Inflation indirectly influenced credit growth through policy tightening and deteriorating borrower purchasing power,

suppressing long-run private credit demand (Coibion et al., 2020).

GDP Growth and Credit Growth Nexus

Counter-Cyclicality of Credit: An expansion in economic activity is associated with an increase in credit demand and lending by financial institutions, while economic slowdowns see a contraction in credit growth.

Interpretation: Credit growth slowed during recessions as declining borrower net worth and economic uncertainty tightened lending conditions and suppressed loan demand (Mian et al., 2017).

Dominance Over Monetary Variables

Empirical evidence shows that GDP growth is more influential in determining credit growth than any other policy factor (Rachuba, 2020).

Interpretation: Credit growth in India demonstrated a demand-pulling nature, with monetary policy playing an accommodating rather than a leading role, as real sector activity and borrower demand consistently drove lending expansion (Das, 2018).

Descriptive Statistical Analysis

- Credit growth shows the highest variance.
- Repo rate and CRR exhibit stability relative to macro variables.
- GDP growth shows extreme volatility due to shocks.

Interpretation: High variability in credit growth confirmed its vulnerability to economic shocks and business cycles, with demand recovery identified as essential for credit revival alongside structural balance sheet repair (Goyal & Verma, 2018).

Correlation Structure Analysis

Direction and Strength

- Negative correlation between repo rates and credit growth.
- Positive correlation between the growth of GDP and credit growth.
- Negative relationship between inflation and growth of credit.

Interpretation of Correlation Limitations: Correlation confirmed the direction of associations between monetary policy variables and credit growth, measuring statistical association rather than causation, with findings aligned with theoretically expected economic relationships (Bhusal, 2025).

Regression Analysis

Impact of Repo Rate

- Statistically significant negative coefficient.
- It makes it evident that higher interest rates limit borrowing.

Impact of CRR

- Negative but weaker impact.
- It implies that liquidity constraints are important, but less than demand effects.

Impact of Inflation

- Slight negative impact.
- It expresses an indirect influence via expectations and policy positions.

Impact of GDP Growth

- Strength and importance of most coefficients.
- Emphasizes the demand side

Interpretation: The effect on credit growth was found to be

condition-dependent, with economic growth emerging as the dominant driver of bank lending behaviour, inducing credit expansion during booms and contractions during downturns (Nguyen et al., 2022; Mian et al., 2017).

Asymmetry in Monetary Transmission

Tightening Phases

- Stiff rise in loan rates.
- Slower loan demand growth.
- Effective transmission of the tightening of monetary policy through higher borrowing costs and credit expansion, which is moderated.

Easing Phases

- Stagnated reduction in the rate on loans despite policy rate cuts
- Banks focus on protecting their margins
- Weak transmission of accommodative monetary policy to lending rates and credit demand

Interpretation: Policy transmission in India remained non-linear and asymmetric, being slow and incomplete, with tightening phases producing stronger and faster credit responses than easing phases across the study period (Khundrakpam, 2017).

Structural Break Analysis

2016 - Demonetization and Flexible Inflation Targeting

- Liquidity shock disrupted the normal transmission.
- Structural break was present in credit behavior.

2020 - COVID Shock

- Credit demand collapsed to its lowest levels in over a decade.
- The tools of policy failed to promote lending.

2022 - Hawkish Cycle

- Growth in credits was robust even as interest rates were hiked
- This signifies dominant recovery demand.

Interpretation: Structural breaks in 2016, 2020, and 2022 confirmed that demonetization, pandemic shocks, and recovery demand each disrupted conventional monetary transmission, rendering policy tools state-dependent and conditionally effective rather than uniformly influential (Lakayil & Shree, 2024).

Conclusion

This study examined the impact of the Reserve Bank of India's monetary policy on credit growth in Indian commercial banks over the period 2010-2025. Based on the results obtained by employing multiple methods of analysis, the efficiencies and asymmetries in the monetary policy channel under various economic conditions, reforms, and shocks were analysed. The study produced several key findings about the nature of credit growth in the Indian banking system.

Empirical results indicated that RBI monetary policy influenced credit growth, though not mechanically and systematically. Changes in policy rate and liquidity by RBI might affect lenders' behaviour. From the lens of prospect theory, lenders evaluated the signals of monetary policy relative to reference points, for example, past interest rates, and expected profitability. During tightening phases, banks became more sensitive to potential credit risk and defaults than to equivalent gains due to loss aversion. This led to conservative lending even when liquidity was available. During easing phases,

though, risk aversion, which worked on the side of gains, led to cautious credit expansion despite policy rates being lower.

In terms of magnitude and timing, however, it depended mainly on the macro-economic conditions, banking sector conditions, and external events. Credit growth in the Indian economy was identified as state-dependent, rather than as monetary policy driven. Although the impact of monetary policy largely influenced the direction of borrowing costs and liquidity, actual credit growth largely relied on demand factors such as economic growth, confidence, and incomes.

Effectiveness of Policy Rate Transmission

The study finds that the transmission of policy rates to credit growth was incomplete and asymmetric. Repo rate hikes were transmitted more quickly and effectively to lending rates and borrowing behaviour than repo rate cuts. In tightening cycles, higher interest rates promptly raised borrowing costs and moderated credit demand. Conversely, in easing cycles, banks often delayed or partially passed on rate cuts in view of margin considerations, risk aversion, and balance-sheet constraints. Hence, the capability of the accommodative monetary policy to influence credit growth during a slowdown was relatively weak, whereas a restrictive policy was more efficacious in keeping the growth of excess credit under control. In this way, it significantly impaired the counter-cyclical role of monetary policy.

Role of Liquidity Measures

Liquidity instruments like CRR, SLR, and open market operations determined banks' lending capacity, especially in the short run. However, excess liquidity, as seen from this analysis, did not transmit into higher credit growth. Episodes of demonetization and COVID-19-related liquidity surge indicated that when economic uncertainty was high and borrower demand was weak, banks would rather deploy their surplus funds in risk-free government securities rather than extend credit. Hence, liquidity measures were a *sine qua non* for sustained credit expansion.

Dominance of Economic Growth in Credit Behaviour

A major result emanating from this research was that the growth in GDP appeared to be the most dominant factor in influencing credit growth, dwarfing the effects of monetary policy variables. Credit growth in India exhibited synchronization with the economic cycle, accelerating during economic recovery and slowing down during an economic downturn. The pro-cyclical behavior of credit revealed that while easing, no matter how forceful, could not trigger credit acceleration in an inactive economy, an active economy could sustain credit acceleration even while raising interest rates.

Implications for Further Research

Although the present study presents a holistic examination of the influence of RBI's monetary policies on the growth of credits in Indian commercial banks, certain domains also emerge, which can lead to further advances in the subject of monetary policies in relation to the growth of credits in Indian commercial banks.

Bank-Level and Ownership-Based Analysis

This study uses aggregated data on credit extended by scheduled commercial banks. Future studies could further disaggregate the growth of credit extended by the different structures of these banks—public sector, private sector, or foreign banks. This would shed light

on differences in their capitalization, different structures of management, and their appetite for risk.

Effects of Global Financial Conditions

Future research might also include global variables like global interest rates, capital flow effects, or exchange rate volatility to quantify the implications of global monetary conditions in the transmission of credit in an increasingly integrated world economy.

Micro-Level Borrower Behaviour

Lastly, research focusing on the borrower side, for example, elasticity of demand for credit, perceiving the risk, and repayment capacity, may provide the micro-economic basis for the weak sensitivity of credit to expansionary monetary policy in a recession.

References

- Ansari, M. G., & Sensarma, R. (2025). Monetary policy, interbank liquidity, and lending behavior of banks in India. *Journal of Emerging Market Finance*, 24(1), 1-32. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09726527241306552>
- Bhusal, T. P. (2025). Correlation does not imply causation: An econometric perspective. *The International Research Journal of Management Science*, 10(1), 39-49. <https://doi.org/10.3126/irjms.v10i1.87259>
- Borio, C., Furfine, C., & Lowe, P. (2001). Procyclicality of the financial system and financial stability: Issues and policy options. *BIS Papers*, 1, 1-57.
- Chattopadhyay, S. K., & Sensarma, R. (2023). Monetary policy transmission in India under the base rate and MCLR regimes. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-01883-9>
- Chodorow-Reich, G., Gopinath, G., Mishra, P., & Narayanan, A. (2020). Cash and the economy: Evidence from India's demonetization. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 135(1), 57-103. <https://doi.org/10.1093/qje/qjz027>
- Çolak, G., & Öztekin, Ö. (2021). The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on bank lending around the world. *Journal of Banking and Finance*, 133, 106207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbankfin.2021.106207>
- Coibion, O., Gorodnichenko, Y., & Ropele, T. (2020). Inflation expectations and firm decisions: New causal evidence. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 135(1), 165-219. <https://doi.org/10.1093/qje/qjz029>
- Creswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, V. L. (2018). The design and conduct of mixed methods research. In J. W. Creswell and V. L. Plano Clark (Eds.), *SAGE handbook of mixed methods in social and behavioral research* (Vol. 2, pp. 1-24). Sage Publications.
- Das, S. (2018). *Monetary policy in India: Transmission to bank interest rates* (RBI Occasional Paper No. 39). Reserve Bank of India. https://www.rbi.org.in/Scripts/bs_viewcontent.aspx?Id=3539
- Deb, P., Estefania-Flores, J., Firat, M., Furceri, D., & Kothari, S. (2023). *Monetary policy transmission heterogeneity: Cross-country evidence* (IMF Working Paper No. WP/23/204). International Monetary Fund. <https://doi.org/10.5089/9798400257322.001>
- Dua, P. (2020). Monetary policy framework in India. *Journal of Quantitative Economics*, 18(3), 475-498. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40953-020-00215-9>
- Eichengreen, B., & Gupta, P. (2024). Inflation targeting in India: A further assessment. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 59(42), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00252921241289522>
- Goyal, A., & Verma, A. (2018). Slowdown in bank credit growth: Aggregate demand or bank non-performing assets? *Margin: The Journal of Applied Economic Research*, 12(3), 257-290. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0973801018768985>
- Gupta, P. (2017). Demonetization and its impact on the Indian economy. *Asian Economic Policy Review*, 12(2), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aep.12189>
- Gupta, P., Sengupta, N., & Roy, R. (2020). COVID-19 and the Indian economy: Impact on growth, manufacturing, trade and MSME sector. *Global Business Review*, 21(5), 1159-1183. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0972150920957157>
- Kahneman, D., & Tversky, A. (1979). Prospect theory: An analysis of decision under risk. *Econometrica*, 47(2), 263-291. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1914185>
- Kasana, E., Chauhan, K., & Sahoo, B. P. (2023). Policy interest rate and bank profitability Scheduled commercial banks in India. *Finance Theory and Practice*, 27(1), 138-149. <https://doi.org/10.26794/2587-5671-2023-27-1-138-149>
- ResearchGate
- Khundrakpam, J. K. (2017). Examining the asymmetric impact of monetary policy in India. *Margin: The Journal of Applied Economic Research*, 11(3), 241-265. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0973801017703500>
- Kumar, A., Prakash, A., & Latey, S. (2022). Monetary transmission to banks' interest rates: Implications of the external benchmark. *Reserve Bank of India Bulletin*, 76(3), 37-52. https://www.rbi.org.in/Scripts/BS_ViewBulletin.aspx
- Lakayil, C., & Shree, M. (2024). Repo rate hike in the post-COVID period and its impact on the lending rate of banks in India. *Journal of Lifestyle and SDGs Review*, 4(4), e03541. <https://doi.org/10.47172/2965-730X.SDGsReview.v4.n04.pe03541>
- Levine, R., Loayza, N., & Beck, T. (2000). Financial intermediation and growth: Causality and causes. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 46(1), 31-77. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3932\(00\)00017-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3932(00)00017-9)
- Menard, S. (2002). *Longitudinal research*. Sage University Papers Series on Quantitative Applications in the Social Sciences, 070-76. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Mian, A., Sufi, A., & Verner, E. (2017). Household debt and business cycles worldwide. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 132(4), 1755-1817. <https://doi.org/10.1093/qje/qjx017>
- Mishra, P., & Montiel, P. (2013). How effective is monetary transmission in low-income countries? A survey of the empirical evidence. *Economic Systems*, 37(2), 187-216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecosys.2012.12.002>
- Mishra, P., Montiel, P., & Sengupta, R. (2016). *Monetary transmission in developing countries: Evidence from India* (IMF Working Paper No. WP/16/167). International Monetary Fund. <https://doi.org/10.5089/9781475523966.001>
- Mitra, A. K., & Chattopadhyay, S. K. (2020). *Monetary policy transmission in India Recent trends and impediments*. RBI Bulletin, March 2020, Vol. LXXIV-3. Reserve Bank of India
- Mohanty, D. (2015). *Monetary policy in India: Transmission to bank interest rates* (RBI Working Paper Series No. WPS (DEPR): 01/2015). Reserve Bank of India. <https://rbidocs.rbi.org.in/rdocs/Publications/PDFs/WP012015.pdf>
- Nguyen, V. H. T., Boateng, A., & Newton, D. (2022). Involuntary excess reserves, the reserve requirements and credit supply: Evidence from Vietnamese commercial banks. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 22(1), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09603107.2015.1060885>
- Patra, M. D., Bhattacharyya, I., Behera, H., & Joshi, H. (2024). Monetary policy transmission in India: Recent evidence. *Reserve Bank of India Bulletin*, 78(10), 15-34. https://rbi.org.in/Scripts/BS_ViewBulletin.aspx
- Prasad, E. S. (2023). India's economy and the global monetary tightening cycle. *Journal of Asian Economics*, 86, 101602. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asieco.2023.101602>
- Rachuba, J. (2020). GDP growth as a bank loan quality determinant. *Journal of Banking and Financial Economics*, 2(14), 21-37. <https://doi.org/10.7172/2353-6845.jbfe.2020.2.2>
- Sengupta, R., Vardhan, H., & Verma, A. (2025). Bank capital and monetary policy transmission: Analyzing the central bank's dilemma. *Economic Modelling*, 152, 107158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econmod.2025.107158>

Received February 14, 2026

Revision received March 3, 2026

Accepted March 5, 2026